

EXPERIMENTAL INVESTIGATION OF UNSTEADY FLOW IN A TRANSONIC COMPRESSOR CASCADE WITH OSCILLATING BLADES USING HIGH-SPEED TWO-WAVELENGTH INTERFEROMETRY

Jindřich Hála

Institute of Thermomechanics
Czech Academy of Sciences
Prague, Czech Republic

Pavel Psota

Faculty of Mechatronics,
Informatics and Interdisciplinary Studies,
Technical University of Liberec, Czech Republic

David Šimurda

Institute of Thermomechanics
Czech Academy of Sciences
Prague, Czech Republic

Petr Šidlof

Faculty of Mechatronics,
Informatics and Interdisciplinary Studies,
Technical University of Liberec, Czech Republic

Jan Lepicovsky

Institute of Thermomechanics
Czech Academy of Sciences
Prague, Czech Republic

ABSTRACT

This study presents experimental results from high-speed interferometric measurements on a transonic compressor blade cascade, where three of the five blades were torsionally oscillated at various frequencies up to 150Hz and different inter-blade phase angles. The resulting flow field images demonstrate the potential of the method. Compared to classical interferometric methods, the present approach is less demanding on the quality of the test section optical windows, enabling measurements even with organic-glass windows which are required for e.g., investigation of highly-loaded compressor blade cascades to accommodate suction slots necessary for maintaining representative value of the Axial Velocity Density Ratio (AVDR). Unlike the classical schlieren technique, the method provides quantitative results with high spatial and temporal resolution, while the synthetic schlieren images can also be produced. The method proved suitable for measurements in the harsh environment of transonic flow through oscillating blades and is capable of capturing important unsteady flow phenomena.

Keywords: Unsteady Aerodynamics, Axial Compressor, Linear Cascade, Two-Wavelength Interferometry

NOMENCLATURE

α_b amplitude of the blade oscillation motion
 γ specific heat ratio
 ρ density
 f_b blade oscillation frequency
 K Gladstone-Dale constant
 M_{is} isentropic Mach number
 n refractive index
 p pressure
subscript 0 total conditions
subscript 1 cascade inlet conditions

1 INTRODUCTION

Understanding the unsteady aerodynamic phenomena in transonic compressor cascades is crucial for advancing turbomachinery design and performance. This study focuses on the experimental analysis of the unsteady flow field within a linear transonic compressor cascade, specifically examining the effects of oscillating blades on flow dynamics. Building on prior research that used optical measurement techniques to visualize transonic airflow in stationary cascades [1], the present investigation introduces controlled oscillations of three blades within the cascade at varying frequencies and phase shifts. The experiments are con-

FIGURE 1: SCHEME OF THE TEST SECTION WITH 5 TRANSONIC COMPRESSOR BLADES.

ducted at a design inlet Mach number $M_1 \sim 1.09$ and blade oscillation amplitude $\alpha_b = 0.25^\circ$.

EXPERIMENTAL SETUP

In this study, the blade flutter test facility at the Institute of Thermomechanics of the Czech Academy of Sciences, located in the High-Speed Laboratory in Nový Knín, was used [2, 3]. The facility comprises a linear cascade with five adjustable blades capable of prescribed oscillatory motions (Fig. 1). The blades represent the midsection of a DFVLR transonic compressor stage rotor at 45% of the blade height [4]. The geometrical and design flow parameters of this MCA-type blade cascade are given in Table 1. The central three blades are actuated by high-speed asynchronous electric motor to oscillate at controlled frequencies and phase shifts, allowing for a detailed study of blade movement on the unsteady flow field. The oscillation parameters can be varied and measured using a laser vibrometer sensor. Additionally, the middle blade (No.3) is instrumented with seven Kulite high-speed pressure sensors on the suction side mid plane, while the neighbouring blades have static pressure taps on the surface connected to NetScanner 9116 pressure transducer. Static pressure is also measured at multiple locations upstream and downstream of the cascade, while total pressure is measured at the inlet to the test section. The entire test section assembly is mounted in a modular in-draft type, open-circuit wind tunnel (Fig. 2).

MEASUREMENT TECHNIQUES

For measurement, a high-speed [5], two-wavelength interferometric technique [6] with an extended range of unambiguity that still achieves single-wavelength accuracy was used. This method employs a high-speed camera to enable short exposure times, effectively avoiding motion blur in the interference patterns and minimizing the influence of environmental disturbances [7]. Fiber optics are used to ensure the compactness and portability of the interferometric system. Quantitative data are

TABLE 1: BLADE CASCADE GEOMETRY AND DESIGN PARAMETERS.

inlet Mach number M_1	1.09
inlet flow angle β_1	148.5°
flow turning angle θ	12.5°
stagger angle γ	48.5°
pitch-chord ratio t/c	0.621

FIGURE 2: SCHEME OF THE MODULAR WIND TUNNEL: 1-SILICA-GEL DRYER, 2-PEBBLE AND CLOTH FILTER, 3-BELL-MOUTH INLET, 4-HONEYCOMB AND SCREEN, 5-CONTRACTION AND CROSS-SECTION CHANGE, 6-TEST SECTION, 7-DIFFUSER, 8-CONTROL NOZZLE, 9-QUICK ACTING BALL VALVE, 10-DIFFUSER, 11-PIPE CONNECTION TO VACUUM CHAMBER.

obtained in a single shot using spatial-carrier frequency techniques and Fourier analysis. A robust approach is introduced for retrieving the unwrapped phase map over an extended unambiguity range while maintaining single-wavelength accuracy. The procedure involves wrapping the difference between the synthetic and single-wavelength phases into the $2/\pi$ interval, followed by spatial unwrapping of the resulting low-density fringe pattern. This method is more robust than standard techniques, which tend to fail when the slope of the phase difference between the synthetic and single-wavelength phase maps exceeds π radians. The interferometer setup is shown in Figure 3.

PRELIMINARY RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Initial measurements from previous experiments on stationary cascades have demonstrated the potential of the high-speed interferometric technique in capturing detailed flow structures, including shock waves and boundary layer interactions [1]. The current study extends this approach to oscillating blades. The recent measurements were carried out for two different inter blade

FIGURE 3: SCHEME OF THE INTERFEROMETER SETUP (BS–BEAM SPLITTER, CAM– HIGH-SPEED CAMERA, FF–FIBER FERRULE, FS–FIBER-SPLITTER, LO, L1, L2–LENSES).

phase angles (IBPA = $\pm 90^\circ$) and three blade oscillation frequencies ($f_b = 50, 100, \text{ and } 150 \text{ Hz}$) with the oscillation amplitude set to 0.25° . For each regime, a sequence in the length of several blade oscillation periods was captured using FASTCAM SA-Z 2100K M64GB monochrome high-speed camera sampling at 30kHz. The resulting interferograms (Figure 4), showing the fringes representing the levels of the constant refractive index n , were evaluated using the Gladstone-Dale equation (1) linking refractive index to density [8].

$$n - 1 = K\rho \quad (1)$$

Then, knowing the density $\rho(x, y)$ and the total density ρ_0 at the inlet, the distribution of the isentropic Mach number $M_{is}(x, y)$ can be easily obtained from the equation

$$M_{is} = \sqrt{\frac{2}{\gamma - 1} \left[\left(\frac{\rho}{\rho_0} \right)^{\gamma - 1} - 1 \right]} \quad (2)$$

The resulting distributions of isentropic Mach number near the middle blade (No. 3) are shown in Figures 5 and 6 for three selected regimes: (i) IBPA = 90° , $f_b = 50 \text{ Hz}$; (ii) IBPA = -90° , $f_b = 50 \text{ Hz}$; and (iii) IBPA = 90° , $f_b = 150 \text{ Hz}$. For each regime, the snapshots correspond to the time instant when the middle blade is at either its maximum positive or negative deflection. In Figure 5a, the most prominent flow features are indicated, including bow shocks upstream of the blades and lip shocks originating at the junction between the rounded trailing edge and the blade surface.

Although only small differences are visible across these cases, it can be noted that for maximum negative deflection of the middle blade, a stronger expansion appears on the forward part of the pressure side compared with positive deflection. This

FIGURE 4: EXAMPLE INTERFEROGRAM OBTAINED DURING THE CURRENT MEASUREMENTS.

effect is more pronounced for IBPA = -90° , as blade No. 2 (not visible) is moving from maximum positive deflection toward its neutral position, whereas for IBPA = 90° , blade No. 2 is moving from maximum negative deflection (resulting in an open inter-blade channel between blades No. 2 and 3) toward its neutral position.

The influence of oscillation frequency is illustrated in Figure 6, which shows the isentropic Mach number distribution for IBPA = 90° and $f_b = 150 \text{ Hz}$. Again, the changes in shock position between limiting deflections are relatively small, but the movement is more pronounced than at $f_b = 50 \text{ Hz}$. It is not clear whether this effect is due to flow phenomena or to increased blade deflection caused by elastic deformation during torsional oscillation. The vibrometer measured a mid-span deflection amplitude of $\sim 0.36^\circ$ for an excitation setting of 0.25° .

It should also be noted that the flow field changes between different periods; therefore, statistical evaluation is required to obtain representative data.

CONCLUSIONS

While much of the data still await rigorous analysis integrating optical and unsteady pressure measurements, the present method has already demonstrated its ability to reveal intricate unsteady flow patterns and shock oscillations in blade flutter research.

Future objectives include adjusting the two-wavelength interferometric technique to larger field of view to visualize larger portion of the cascade. In the current setup, it is also difficult to visualize the flow near the blade surface, as the organic-glass

FIGURE 5: Resulting isentropic Mach number distributions for $IBPA = 90^\circ$; $f_b = 50\text{ Hz}$, maximal positive **a)** and negative deflection **b)** and for $IBPA = -90^\circ$; $f_b = 50\text{ Hz}$, maximal positive **c)** and negative deflection **d)**.

sealing plate required for the oscillating blade setup wears out quickly and obstructs a clear view of this region. This is not a problem in case of stationary blades, therefore, other test-case might be used for study of the shock wave oscillations not induced by blade forced motion. The great advantage of this method is in its low demands on the quality of the optical windows enabling it for use in the compressor research in which suction slots need to be cut into the side-walls to suppress undesirable effects of flow contraction [9].

The findings contribute to a deeper understanding of flutter phenomena in transonic compressor cascades, offering valuable

insights for the design and analysis of turbomachinery components. The data might also be of utmost importance for validation of the high-fidelity computational codes which are increasingly used to study the flutter phenomena.

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

The authors would like to acknowledge the support of the Czech Science Foundation (GACR) under grant no. 24-11973S. Institutional support of the Institute of Thermomechanics of the Czech Academy of Sciences RVO:61388998 is also gratefully acknowledged.

FIGURE 6: Resulting isentropic Mach number distributions for $IBPA = 90^\circ$; $f_b = 150\text{Hz}$, maximal positive a) and negative deflection b).

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